

Gating strategy of GATA3⁺ CD4 T cells (Th2) and Foxp3⁺ CD4 T cells (T reg)

online repository file 2. A gating strategy to determine the abundance of Th2 and T reg. Th2 were identified as CD45⁺ CD3⁺ CD4⁺ GATA3⁺ cells, and T reg were identified as CD45⁺ CD3⁺ CD4⁺ Foxp3⁺ cells.